

HyDelta

WP 4 The development of educational tracks

D4.1 The requirements for MBO technical personnel and advice for strengthening hydrogen education on MBO-level.

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Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Suzanne van Greuningen
Affiliation	Consultant, Kiwa Technology
Email address	Suzanne.van.greuningen@kiwa.com

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Document review

Partner	Name
Alliander	Bart Vogelzang
Alliander	Rick Marsman
Alliander	Rene Oussoren
Stedin	Frank van Alphen
Stedin	Ed Verhagen
Gasunie	Marcel Heikens
Gasunie	Marcel Smit
Gasunie	Dolf Ottens

Executive summary

In the field of infrastructure technology (distribution of energy in the form of (methane) gas, heat and electricity) for hydrogen, no comprehensive and adequate intermediate vocational education, or MBO (*note: hereinafter referred to MBO according to Dutch education system*), is currently offered by educational training institutions. However, the demand will increase in the coming years for technically trained personnel at MBO level who possess the knowledge and skills of a natural gas network, a hydrogen network and network conversion, in order to achieve the goals of converting the natural gas network to hydrogen. In the coming years, operational deployment of technicians with this knowledge will be required by the national energy network operator for realising the hydrogen backbone. This necessity also applies to the regional network operators, whose hydrogen pilot projects require several teams of technicians with this knowledge to be deployed in the near future and a potential hydrogen distribution network offers future prospects for growth in this number. Immediate action therefore has to be taken to train current staff and to train additional technical personnel with knowledge of natural gas and hydrogen distribution.

Training courses can be developed in collaboration with the professional field which facilitates for adapting to changes. An additional advantage is that this can also be used on a small scale, which makes it suitable for the planned pilot projects. Courses that cover the basic knowledge of hydrogen and the differences compared to natural gas are part of the training courses and study programmes currently available. This means that a first introduction to hydrogen can already be taught using the educational training that is already present within the network organisation schools themselves, or through the options below.

- Training Waterstof (Noorderpoort): a 10-day course that discusses the operation, advantages and disadvantages and transport and application possibilities of hydrogen.
- Praktijkcursus Waterstof (Kiwa Training): a one-day practical training in which the properties of hydrogen and differences with natural gas are approached from a theoretical as well as a practical perspective (by means of practical tests).

A comprehensive and adequate MBO education for technical personnel is not available and will need to be developed. The required attainment targets serve as the basis for every training course and study programme. These attainment targets are specified in Chapter 5. They are the basis for electives and refresher courses for technicians who will be working on high-pressure and low-pressure hydrogen pipelines. General knowledge about hydrogen, (changes in) technical process steps and safe working procedures are central topics. A detailed elaboration of the attainment targets in the form of learning objectives can be further developed after establishing national safety work instructions (SWIs) for hydrogen and after clarifying the technical specifications.

Attention should also be paid to recruiting personnel in the field of infrastructure technology. There is a shortage of both technical staff and teachers to train them. This scarcity already prevails in the energy sector, but extends to personnel with hydrogen expertise. In order to actually realise the hydrogen projects and ambitions, the technical staff and teachers to train them must be available.

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1. Introduction

HyDelta work package 4 concentrates on hydrogen and educational development. In order to manage the size of the project, it was important to choose a suitable scope. The network operators have indicated that the area with the greatest need to develop hydrogen education is in intermediate vocational education (MBO), specifically for technicians in the infrastructure and distribution sector. It is with this need in mind that the project's main focus is on this target group.

To be able give well-founded advice on and make a substantive contribution to expanding and revising the current curricula, it is essential to perform a gap analysis. The gap analysis takes into account the expected requirements, the current status and the size of the educational programmes on offer.

Insight into the future need for this type of technical operational personnel was obtained through a literature review. The technical workforce that the infrastructure and distribution sector may need depends on how the Dutch hydrogen market and economy evolve in the years to come. Using available modelling studies, the various scenarios of these developments have been translated into labour demand, thus providing an estimate of the potential demand for one-off and recurrent labour related to green hydrogen in the Netherlands. You can find the outcomes in Chapter 2.

In order to fully understand the current status and extent of the hydrogen curriculum in the MBO educational landscape, an inventory was made of study programmes, facilities and practical test locations. This was done by conducting internet research and interviews, the findings of which are summarised in Chapter 3.

The gap analysis that relates the future need for technical operational personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector to the current status and scope of the technical curriculum is set out in Chapter 4. The previously investigated potential demand for one-off and recurrent labour and the inventory of study programmes, facilities and practical test locations at MBO level form the basis to this end.

Chapter 5 provides additional information on the currently available educational offers in the form of learning outcomes for study programmes for technical operations personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector. By educating and training according to the attainment targets below, technical personnel will be sufficiently prepared for working in hydrogen distribution.

2. Potential labour demand for MBO-level technically skilled personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector.

2.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises the literature review on the potential labour demand for technically skilled personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector, specifically related to the use of hydrogen in the Netherlands in 2030 and 2050. Several studies have been conducted in recent years that look into the potential development of the hydrogen market and the hydrogen value chain as a whole. However, only a handful of the resulting future scenarios have been studied in further detail and linked to the labour demand that arises from those developments. Where this has been done, the detail level (sector-specific, level of education, etc.) of the demand for labour varies greatly. CE Delft recently presented a study in which the labour demand was divided into different sectors and the modelled gross jobs were largely attributable to technically skilled personnel (MBO engineering technology). The results of that study form the main basis for this work package. A distinction has been made between the one-off demand for labour (for conversion and construction) and recurring demand for labour (for maintenance and operation) across the entire value chain of green hydrogen. The demand for labour is expressed in average full-time equivalents (FTE) per year over the coming years.

2.2 Outcomes

General labour demand for energy transition

“Investment plan Waterstof Noord”

According to the *Investment Plan Waterstof Noord*, if the Netherlands takes the lead in developing a European hydrogen ecosystem, it can create opportunities to capture and attract new business and jobs [1]. Developing the hydrogen ecosystem could yield up to 104,000 FTEs in one-off jobs between 2020 and 2050 (see Table 1). Furthermore, if we look at recurrent employment, a total of 66,000 existing FTEs can be retained and 41,000 new FTEs attracted. These projections do not distinguish between the different sectors and education levels. It is therefore impossible to determine what proportion can be attributed to technically skilled personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector.

The same study also investigated how upscaling and expanding the hydrogen ecosystem could benefit employment in the north of the Netherlands until 2025 and the five years thereafter. For the sake of completeness, that labour demand has also been included in Table 1.

“Employment through investments in green hydrogen”

A study by CE Delft from April 2021 provides a more detailed estimate [2]. The modelled potential demand for labour is broken down by sector and the associated FTEs are for the most part attributable to technically skilled personnel. This study also provides more insight into the scenarios on which the labour demand is based. The potential (general) labour demand is related to the development of the demand for hydrogen. Two different scenarios have been taken as a starting point: a high and a low scenario. The low scenario looks at both minimal use and minimal (Dutch) production of green hydrogen. The high scenario looks at both maximum use and maximum own production. Table 1 shows the total demand for labour in 2030, 2040 and 2050 for both scenarios. One can clearly see that there

is a significant difference between the high and low scenarios, but also that there will be a substantial demand for one-off and recurrent labour in both scenarios. It is worth noting that the demand for labour in 2040 and 2050 increases by at least a factor of four compared to (only) a doubling of the demand for hydrogen. This disproportionate relationship is explained by a higher share of upstream in the Netherlands, but also the effect of the difference between limited use and predominant use in the mobility and built environment sectors. In those two sectors, a relatively limited demand for hydrogen has a major effect on the demand for labour. Both are relatively 'labour-intensive' sectors [2]. The labour that is included in the built environment sector will be needed for modifications to systems in end-users' homes and for the production of boilers and installation of hybrid heat pumps. The latter accounts for the largest share of labour demand. Modifications to the distribution network are not included and are covered separately below.

Table 1. Potential demand for labour taken from the 'Investment Plan Hydrogen North' [Dutch: Investeringsplan Waterstof Noord] and 'Employment through investments in green hydrogen' [Dutch: Werk door investeringen in groene waterstof]. * Relates to both one-off and recurrent labour demand.

Year	Region	Demand for green hydrogen (PY)	One-off labour demand (in FTEs/year)	Recurrent labour demand (in FTEs/year)
<2030	The Netherlands [1]		2,500 FTEs	22,500 FTEs
2020-2050	The Netherlands [1]		104,000 FTEs	66,000 FTEs retaining existing jobs 41,000 FTEs new jobs
2020-2025	North-NL [1]		~5,000 FTEs*	
2025-2030	North-NL [1]		~25,000 FTEs*	
2030	The Netherlands [2]	10-40	1,800–4,700 (low–high)	4,200–12,500 (low–high)
2040	The Netherlands [2]	132-317	2,000–13,000 (low–high)	9,200–43,000 (low–high)
2050	The Netherlands [2]	254-593	2,200–20,000 (low–high)	14,200–72,600 (low–high)

Future labour demand in the infrastructure and transport sector

The investments in green hydrogen will have an impact on the availability of labour throughout the chain, and therefore on the technical operational staff of the national and regional network operators. A number of scenario studies have been carried out at European and national level, which look into the effects that various climate measures have for the labour market. All forms of green energy are taken into account and the studies do not focus purely on hydrogen. In addition, the scale of focus is relatively broad in the studies, for example the 'oil and gas industry'.

Model studies that look specifically at employment of technically educated personnel (MBO level) are very limited. In an extensive search, only one model study was found to be representative and usable.

The most detailed figures on future potential labour demand in the infrastructure and transport sector can be found in the study by CE Delft [2]. The study distinguishes between establishing a hydrogen

backbone, modifying the distribution network, and maintaining and operating the entire gas transport network. Furthermore, the study mentions that a large proportion of the labour demand consists of technically trained personnel (MBO). Estimates of future labour demand in CE Delft's study are based among other things on investment plans by Gasunie [3], Kiwa [4] and figures of Statistics Netherlands. [5].

Hydrogen backbone

The hydrogen backbone will have to facilitate and accelerate hydrogen use in the Netherlands, including setting up connections to industrial regions. It will also enable the Netherlands to play a key role as a transit channel in distributing the hydrogen to international destinations. The backbone plays a crucial part in both the high and low scenarios, which is why the labour demand for conversion has been included in both the high and low scenarios (see table 2). It is expected that from 2024 to 2030, between 455 and 690 people a year will find employment in the various conversion projects of the gas transport network [2]. This is a one-off labour demand for preparing the hydrogen backbone for the future; the recurrent demand is discussed in the final section.

Hydrogen distribution network

Only very minor adjustments are needed to make the gas distribution network in built-up environments suitable for hydrogen. The necessary adjustments are concentrated mainly in the gas meter of end-users and, to a lesser extent, around gas receiving stations. According to the CE Delft study, the use of hydrogen in built-up environments will only occur in the high scenario, will only play an important role after 2030 and the modifications will therefore also take place after 2030. The one-off labour demand for conversion of the distribution network is estimated at an average of 161 FTEs per annum for the period 2030-2050 (Table 2). This does not include modifications at end users, which fall under industry and indoor installation. It also excludes the construction of hydrogen distribution networks to connect industries to the hydrogen backbone.

Recurrent employment on the hydrogen backbone and distribution network

Maintenance work and operation of the transport and distribution network can be translated into recurrent labour. This is expected to require approximately the same amount of labour as the current natural gas network [2]. The assumption in this forecast is that the capacity of the distribution network remains the same and that the number of jobs also remains stable. Based on the above, it could lead to some 3,500 recurring jobs being by 2040 for maintenance and operation of hydrogen, growing to a maximum of 7,000 (Table 2) in 2050.

Table 2. The total labour demand for conversion and modification of the gas transport and distribution network and the recurrent demand for maintenance and operation of both networks.

	Year	One-off labour demand (in FTEs/year)	Recurrent labour demand (in FTEs/year)
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Construction of hydrogen backbone	2030	573–573 (low–high)	
	2040	0–0 (low–high)	
	2050	0–0 (low–high)	
Modifications to distribution network	2030	0–0 (low–high)	
	2040	0–161 (low–high)	
	2050	0–161 (low–high)	
Maintenance and operation	2030		0–0 (low–high)
	2040		0–3,500 (low–high)
	2050		0–7,000 (low–high)

2020-2030: pilot projects and plans by network operators and Gasunie

It is apparent from discussions with network operators and Gasunie show that their plans also target the shorter term from 2020-2030. Several pilot projects are expected to start in 2022 and even more initiatives are in the pipeline over the next ten years. Gasunie, for example, expects to reach its first milestone in 2024 when its new HyTransPort hydrogen pipeline comes into operation, and network operators already have various pilot projects in place that require technicians, some technical teams, to learn the knowledge and skills of working with hydrogen. The pilot projects below will demand technicians with knowledge of hydrogen during construction and maintenance and are planned for the next few years:

Gasunie

- **Djewels:** facilitating and managing hydrogen infrastructure and storage capacity;
- **GZI Next:** co-developing electrolysis conversion capacity and providing the infrastructure;
- **HyTransPort.RTM:** constructing a new hydrogen pipeline ‘HyTransPort’
- **Magnumcentrale:** converting a power plant from natural gas to hydrogen
- **NorthH2:** a smart storage and transport network in the Netherlands and North-West Europe for green hydrogen. The existing gas network will be made suitable for the storage and transport of hydrogen;
- **RIB Amsterdam:** an open-access, high-pressure hydrogen pipeline connecting De IJmond with the port area of Amsterdam and with the national hydrogen backbone;
- **Hydrogen backbone:** creating a national hydrogen infrastructure that will utilise approximately 85% of the existing natural gas pipelines;
- **Stad aan 't Haringvliet:** Gasunie will provide the link between Oude-Tonge and Stad aan 't Haringvliet; this will be a new pipeline.

Cogas

- **Waterstofwijk Hoogeveen:** First constructing a new pipeline and then converting existing natural gas pipelines to hydrogen in two areas in the municipality of Hoogeveen.

Enexis

- **Woonwijk Wagenborgen:** converting existing gas pipelines to create a hydrogen network from local production, then to storage and consumption in a residential district in hybrid heat pumps during cold periods.
- **The Green Village:** test environment for acquiring knowledge and experience in the management and maintenance of a hydrogen distribution network.

Alliander

- **Lochem:** converting gas pipelines to hydrogen pipelines in order to connect 14 older, heritage-listed buildings to hydrogen gas;
- **The Green Village:** test environment for acquiring knowledge and experience of the management and maintenance of a hydrogen distribution network.

Rendo:

- **Waterstofwijk Hoozeveen:** converting existing natural gas pipelines to hydrogen in two areas in the municipality of Hoozeveen.

Stedin

- **Waterstof in Rozenburg:** converting existing gas pipelines and installation systems to allow the use of hydrogen for heating an apartment complex.
- **The Green Village:** test environment for acquiring knowledge and experience in the management and maintenance of a hydrogen distribution network.
- **Stad aan 't Haringvliet:** step-by-step conversion of the existing natural gas network to supply the town with green, locally produced hydrogen.

The technical implementation phase of the above projects will require technicians and engineers with expertise in hydrogen. It is therefore imperative that detailed plans are made in the very near future in order to understand how many FTEs are for these projects and the specialist knowledge involved. Specific education and training must start immediately afterwards.

Future labour demand: additional or replacement labour?

The regional network operators estimate that there are currently around 12,500 technicians, employed by contractors and network companies collectively, with a VIAG designation (Safety Instructions for Natural Gas). These are mostly full-time positions. A full-time position can be expressed as 1 FTE. This means that in the current market there are approximately 12,500 FTEs working as technical staff. The Gasunie employs a fairly stable base of approximately 500 technicians.

Whether the demand for labour will create 'new, extra jobs' (so-called additional labour) because of the transition to hydrogen, or whether these jobs will replace existing jobs is a question that the CE Delft answers in its theoretical study. The disappearance of jobs in the fossil industry and the creation of new jobs by displacement (inflow from other sectors) are not considered.

Preparing the infrastructure is regarded as additional labour, both for the hydrogen backbone and the distribution network. The maintenance and operation of the natural gas network is regarded as replacement labour.

2.3 Conclusion

There is only a limited number of studies on the future labour demand for MBO technically educated personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector that are related to green hydrogen. The above

information and figures are mainly based on a recent report by CE Delft. The conclusions below are therefore linked to the scenarios in that report and the assumptions arising from that report.

- The one-off labour demand linked to the construction of the hydrogen backbone is estimated at 573 FTEs. These additional jobs are expected to be filled by 2030.
- The one-off labour demand linked to the conversion of the distribution network is estimated at 161 FTEs. This demand for labour only occurs in the 'high scenario', i.e. the scenario that looks at maximum application and maximum own production. It concerns additional jobs over a period of 20 years (2030-2050).
- The recurrent labour demand for operating the hydrogen network and maintenance will mainly be noticeable in the high scenario and will only start in 2040. In 2040, it is estimated that labour demand will be around 3,500 FTE per year, rising to 7,000 FTE in 2050. The recurrent labour demand is seen as replacement labour.
- Looking at the shorter term (2022-2030), there is already an increased demand for hydrogen-educated technicians for the pilot projects initiated by the gas network operators and Gasunie. Taking into account the lead times for training, it is crucial to identify what is needed in terms of technical crews and the knowledge they require.
- A start will also have to be made in the next few years in terms of training the technicians needed for the work on the hydrogen backbone according to the scenario study (2030). Large-scale roll-out of hydrogen in the built environment should not be expected before 2030. Before that year, training for technicians by regional network operators will therefore be limited to pilot project teams.

The gap analysis discusses what this demand for labour in the infrastructure and distribution sector means for the developments in hydrogen education. The gap analysis on this subject can be consulted in Chapter 4.

3. Assessment of current training offerings at MBO level

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contains an inventory of the current supply of hydrogen-related training and education at MBO level (intermediate vocational education). The study was carried out during the first half of 2021 and therefore provides a relatively up-to-date picture of the state of affairs. In addition to the course programmes on offer, the study also looks at projects that are underway between the business community and educational institutes.

For the purpose of the inventory, a website survey was carried out with a large number of the educational institutes operating in the Netherlands at MBO level. The educational institutes were divided as follows:

- Regular educational institutions (ROCs - Regional Education Centres)
- Private educational institutions and vocational schools
- In-company training and education facilities

A selection was made from the list of educational institutions obtained (see [Annex I](#)) of the schools that, according to the website survey, have the most to offer in terms of hydrogen education. The selected educational institutions were contacted for an interview to obtain a more detailed picture of what programmes they offer in the field of hydrogen. A list of the educational institutions contacted and a brief description of their responses can be found in the Annex. A further look was also taken at projects currently in progress within the sector that involves collaborative efforts between the business community and educators. It also looked at the current supply of practical facilities and test locations for the application of hydrogen.

3.2 Outcomes

Projects

There are various projects already under way that focus on hydrogen and education. They involve collaborations with the business community to perform research, promote hydrogen and provide students with more practical facilities.

- The Energy College has started a partnership between seven MBO schools, 50+ companies and government bodies in the north of the Netherlands, and is aimed at motivating young people to be an active part of the energy transition. Besides hydrogen, other themes are discussed such as sustainability, geothermal energy, power-to-gas and biogas. Interested students have access to a free online introduction module about hydrogen.
- Then there is the Green Hydrogen Booster, a consortium of several partners with the Hanzehogeschool in Groningen as its main coordinator. The goal of the consortium is to bring the entire value chain of green hydrogen ideas, innovations, students, educational institutions, SMEs, industry and interested parties together under one roof. The Green Hydrogen Booster offers a range of educational activities, wants to promote the north as an energy region and build test facilities.
- In the short term, the “Hydrogen Works” [*Dutch: Waterstof Werkt*] programme will provide ongoing learning on hydrogen for the North-Netherlands region. It offers study programmes, training and courses at MBO, HBO, WO level (intermediate vocational, higher vocational or university-level education) as well as post-initial level. All educational institutions in the north of the Netherlands are working together to set up a coordinated approach.

- The Green Village is the living lab for sustainable innovations on the TU Delft campus. Here, Stedin, Alliander and Enexis Group are testing the paper conclusions of using hydrogen in a 'normal' gas network. This helps them gain knowledge and experience on how to manage and maintain a hydrogen network in areas where people live and work.
- Kiwa and network operator Alliander have rolled up the sleeves together to build the very first hydrogen demo home in the Netherlands, in Apeldoorn. The Hydrogen Experience Centre is a testing and demo site that is designed as a home, and is also used as a training centre for technicians and installers. It is an ideal facility to teach them how to make the existing natural gas supply in residential areas suitable for hydrogen.
- Other experience centres also exist besides the Hydrogen Experience Centre of Kiwa and Alliander. Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences, for instance, has the H2Energylab on the Innovation Dock. It is a collaboration with companies including RDM Rotterdam, the Port of Rotterdam Authority and Ennology where students from different educational programmes can enrol in practice-oriented studies. Stedin is busy doing tests in Rozenburg and in The Green Village, where they are converting existing homes from natural gas to hydrogen. Entrance is an expertise centre of the Hanzehogeschool in Groningen, where education, research and entrepreneurship are given a testing ground to promote the energy transition. Hydrogen also plays an important role.
- Stedin has the 'Hydrogen in Rozenburg' project that focuses on converting electricity into hydrogen. They are the first party in the Netherlands to apply this technique in a pilot project. Between 2018 and 2023, they are demonstrating the use of hydrogen for heating in existing built-up areas. Two hydrogen boilers have been installed in an existing apartment complex in Rozenberg to demonstrate this technology.
- In addition to the project in Rozenburg, Stedin also has the 'temporary conversion from natural gas to hydrogen' project. In a number of houses due for demolition in Uithoorn, Stedin temporarily converted the existing natural gas network to make it suitable for hydrogen. This provided a more realistic picture of the work required.

There are many projects on education and hydrogen going on at the moment. The focus is on the northern Netherlands, however, and there is not much around specifically for MBO education. The projects are often aimed more at higher education or they combine WO, HBO and MBO. The Hydrogen Experience Centre of Kiwa and Alliander is an exception. Here, facilities have been built to prepare MBO students for practical work with hydrogen.

Regular educational institutions

The majority of regular educators do not offer study programmes on hydrogen (at this stage). It is at most touched on in elective subjects relating to sustainability. The topics of 'sustainability', 'energy transition' and 'hydrogen' are often mentioned in news reports. The regular education facilities that have incorporated hydrogen in their curriculum limit it mainly to "automotive" (mobility) studies. It is often the teacher's personal affinity for the subject that determines whether hydrogen is covered in the course matter and to what extent.

Educators in the northern provinces spend more time and effort on hydrogen than schools in the rest of the Netherlands. This is also reflected in the number of hydrogen projects we have worked on and contacts we have within the ROC (Regional Education and Training Centres). The collaboration is close, not only between the various ROCs but also with higher education, the business community and government authorities. Noorderpoort is already well advanced in the development of hydrogen education at MBO level. An education plan is in place and elective courses are being developed, the first part of which, Hydrogen Technology (basic), is ready and is currently being implemented [6]. The Ozone online module is part of the curriculum and is being used by 15 ROCs. In addition, the following components are covered:

- Hydrogen technology in mobility
- Hydrogen technology in the built environment
- Hydrogen technology in industry
- Hydrogen technology in the energy chain

Many other ROCs in the north of the Netherlands work together, for example in the Energy College. A lot is happening in the field of hydrogen, and many webinars and lectures are being organised. More and more ROCs are also offering elective courses on hydrogen. Alfacollege is involved in the *Waterstof Werkt* (Hydrogen Works) programme and offers hydrogen modules with its school-based Engineering Technician programme (BOL, level 4). Students are also working together on a tiny house that runs on hydrogen and a hydrogen-powered speedboat, and helped with the opening of Hystock, a hydrogen storage pilot of Gasunie. At Drenthe College, many of the teachers have taken additional courses on hydrogen and even offer their hydrogen technology expertise to help industry move forward. On 4 October 2021, Drenthe College hired a dedicated Hydrogen Practitioner who is responsible for hydrogen education. Finding enough staff remains the biggest hurdle. As regards practical locations, there aren't many obstacles on the road. The EnTranCe location can be used for practical education and testing. In addition, medium-sized fuel cell training modules have been ordered from Lucas Nülle (Lucas Nülle - EHY 2 Advanced fuel cell technology (lucas-nuelle.us)). At the ROCs in Friesland, sustainability seems to play a bigger role than specifically hydrogen. Friese Poort has the *Duurzaam Doen Huis* (Sustainable Practices Home), where pupils can learn and work on building sustainably. Unfortunately, hydrogen only plays a minor role.

In the field of infrastructure technology (energy distribution for (natural) gas, heat and electricity), the regular educators do not offer any curricula that focus on hydrogen.

Private educational institutions and vocational schools

Private educators mainly offer e-learning modules, training courses, workshops and master classes that explain the basics of hydrogen and hydrogen application. The content is interesting for participants who work as engineers, consultants, technicians, project leaders, work planners and other professionals working for network operators, government, municipalities, provinces, housing corporations and industrial companies. These courses, workshops and master classes generally cover the following topics:

- The energy transition and the role of hydrogen.
- What is hydrogen?
- Why opt for hydrogen?
- The uses of hydrogen.
- The (physical) characteristics of hydrogen and how they compare to natural gas.
- The role of hydrogen in the energy system.

These are mainly informative, knowledge-based training courses, workshops and master classes aimed at the target groups with an MBO+ and HBO level educational background. Some educators also use practical tests to demonstrate how hydrogen works as an energy source, its applications and the properties of hydrogen.

In private educational institutions and vocational schools that provide training to gas, water and heating engineers, there is very little course material available about hydrogen in energy distribution.

As mentioned earlier in the section on projects and initiatives, a Hydrogen Experience Centre was recently opened in the Netherlands by Kiwa and Alliander. Besides its purpose as a test and demo site, this hydrogen home is also set up as a training location. Kiwa and Alliander are currently developing a

course to train engineers and technicians who work in energy distribution how to convert the natural gas network to a hydrogen network.

In-company training and education facilities

At present, the in-company schools of Enexis, Stedin and Alliander do not offer any standard courses or training on hydrogen. They do organise sessions where basic knowledge about hydrogen is shared with technicians. Additional safety training, which is aimed at enabling technicians with a VIAG designation to work with hydrogen, will be provided mainly by the network companies' own training departments and by contractors. At Stedin, technicians are appointed as part of a "hydrogen head group" on the basis of selection criteria. Gasunie offers internal practical courses for natural gas, but not for hydrogen. It does provide options to enrol in hydrogen courses externally at HBO+ level. Gasunie is seeing a growing need for technical details and the operational engineering divisions are trying to find their future role and how to best educate their own technicians on working safely with hydrogen.

The training courses that in-company schools will be offering to their technicians depend strongly on the Safety Work Instructions (SWIs) that are still being developed for hydrogen. At this stage, not enough is known about the safety requirements that technicians have to meet when working with and on hydrogen pipelines. Risk assessments are first needed before the final training requirements can be determined based on the safety work instructions for hydrogen.

Other obstacles: scarcity on the labour market and complexity of the system

The last point at issue, on top of the limited supply of hydrogen training courses, is the shortage of personnel. This is already apparent in the energy sector; there aren't enough current staff, not enough students and not enough teachers. To avoid personnel shortages for the hydrogen economy, there has to be enough staff in general.

The hydrogen economy is currently still in full development and it is as yet unclear what the future will look like. It is highly likely that other energy carriers will be used besides hydrogen. This means that the energy mix will be more varied in the future. Engineers will therefore not only work with hydrogen, but also with natural gas/green gas, CO₂ and heat. The work will become increasingly complex and technicians need to be prepared in advance. A way of tackling this future challenge is by offering broader education options for mobility, transport/distribution, storage and production, such as a mechanical engineering study with a specialisation in hydrogen.

Separate from the MBO training, additional safety training may be required for everyone with a VIAG designation (Safety Instructions for Natural Gas). The basic assumption here should be that the natural gas technicians currently employed at network companies and contractors will be the ones working in the hydrogen network.

3.3 Conclusion

The assessment reveals that many projects and initiatives are currently underway in the hydrogen field, but that they are mainly aimed at higher education levels or a combination of WO, HBO and MBO (university, higher vocational and intermediate vocational education). Most of the e-learning modules, courses, workshops and master classes that are on offer concentrate on the basics of hydrogen and

hydrogen applications and target mainly MBO+ and HBO students. The focus of most study programmes currently available is on mobility. The most important findings at MBO level are listed below for each educational institution. It is also apparent from the interviews that there is a great need for technically skilled personnel and for teachers to educate and train them.

Regular educational institutions (e.g. ROCs)

- The majority do not have any courses available (yet) that focus on hydrogen. At most, it is briefly touched on in elective subjects on sustainability. In those educational institutions where hydrogen is included in the curriculum, this is mainly limited to transport and mobility courses.
- Noorderpoort, located in the north of the Netherlands, has prepared an educational plan for a hydrogen study programme at MBO level. The first part of the programme: Hydrogen technology (basic) was recently finalised and is being implemented.

Private educational institutions and vocational schools:

- There is currently still little to be found in the way of study courses for gas, water and heat technicians who work in the hydrogen infrastructure and distribution sector.
- Alliander and Kiwa have joined forces and are developing a course to train technicians working in energy distribution to convert the natural gas network to a hydrogen network.

In-company schools:

- The internal company schools of Enexis, Stedin and Alliander presently do not offer any standard courses or training on hydrogen. They do organise sessions where basic knowledge about hydrogen is shared with technicians. Supplementary safety training will mainly be provided by the internal training divisions of the network companies and by contractors.
- Gasunie's in-company school does not offer an operational technical course in hydrogen for technicians, although it does acknowledge that there is a need for such training.

4. Gap analysis of potential demand and current supply of education at MBO level

4.1 Introduction

This gap analysis compares the demand for MBO-educated operational personnel with the currently available options for educating and training such personnel. The potential need distinguishes between one-off and recurrent labour. One-off labour refers to the work that is required in order to convert the gas systems and prepare the networks for hydrogen. Recurrent labour includes jobs related to the operation and maintenance of the networks. The following step involves investigating whether the current range of intermediate vocational education (MBO) is sufficient to provide the required personnel with the appropriate training. A large portion of the MBO-level educational institutions in the Netherlands have been included in this analysis and comprise regular educational institutions (ROCs), private educational institutions and in-house company schools. Recommendations will subsequently be given on adding new training courses and facilities, which will be covered in more detail in the next chapter.

4.2 Outcomes

Labour demand

Potential demand for personnel includes both one-off and recurrent labour for the regional network operators and Gasunie. Labour demand is expressed in average full time equivalents (FTE) per year at a given moment in time. These FTEs can be seen as direct full-time jobs.

As part of the preparation work for the hydrogen backbone, it is expected that 573 FTE per year will be needed in the period 2030-2040. Assuming that the preparation work will have been completed by 2040, the one-off labour demand for this work will decline to zero after then. The one-off labour demand linked to converting the distribution network will be between 0 and a maximum of 161 FTE per year over the period 2030-2050. The recurrent labour demand for operating the hydrogen network and maintenance will mainly be noticeable in the high scenario and will only start in 2040. In 2040, it is estimated that the demand for labour will be around 3,500 FTEs per year, rising to 7,000 FTEs in 2050.

In the most favourable scenario where demand for hydrogen is at its highest, Gasunie will need to consider employing 573 hydrogen-educated technicians from 2030. The regional network operators will need to consider employing 161 hydrogen-trained technicians from 2040 onwards. It is essential that these technicians have specific knowledge about converting the gas networks and receive training in working with natural gas and hydrogen. For maintenance of the grid, Gasunie and the network operators will have to take account of 3,500 gross jobs, with a doubling of that number by 2050.

Hydrogen education

Hydrogen, and particularly its use as a clean energy source, is a subject that is attracting a great deal of interest. This is also reflected in all the different projects, initiatives and people that combine hydrogen and education. However, looking a little deeper into all the enthusiastic stories, it appears that there aren't many relevant courses on offer at present.

Most of what is on offer is in the north of the Netherlands, where elective modules have been developed by the Noorderpoort College. Of these, the 'basic hydrogen module' is now available for students. The module looks at the physical and chemical properties of hydrogen and the options for application.

Hydrogen education for technical staff aimed at the conversion the gas networks and at future maintenance of the networks, whether it concerns MBO-level education or a concrete set-up for such training, have not been identified in the assessment.

Gap analysis

Research into the potential demand for labour shows that technicians will have to be trained in the coming years, so that they are fully prepared for the conversion work on the gas distribution and transport network and to maintain it during the transport of hydrogen. The construction of the hydrogen backbone is already a fact. In order to achieve the ambition of a pipeline network with national coverage by 2030, Gasunie will need to provide comprehensive training or retraining on hydrogen for its technicians over the next few years. This will need to be taken into account from around 2040 for the low-pressure distribution network.

It is clear from the assessment that intermediate vocational education (MBO) has not yet made concrete plans to develop the study courses to cater for this transition. MBO elective courses and refresher courses need to be set up for future hydrogen technicians. In terms of content, these courses should also pay attention to attaining knowledge on hydrogen, but the primary focus should be on teaching the specific knowledge and skills that are needed to convert and later maintain the networks. It is important that the course emphasises the differences between working with hydrogen and working with natural gas.

On top of the limited supply of hydrogen training courses, is the shortage of personnel. This is already apparent in the energy sector; there aren't enough students and not enough teachers. To avoid personnel shortages for the hydrogen economy, there has to be enough staff in general.

The hydrogen economy is currently still in full development and it is as yet unclear what the future will look like. It is highly likely that other energy carriers will be used besides hydrogen. This means that the energy mix will be more varied in the future. Engineers will therefore not only work with hydrogen, but also with natural gas, CO₂ and heat. The work will become increasingly complex and technicians need to be prepared in advance.

Intervision could be a tool that can help tackle this issue. For instance, the courses can be developed based on experiences from the field, making it easier to adapt the course material to the changes. This can also be used on a small scale, considering the fact that the exact demand is still unclear.

4.3 Conclusion

There are currently no courses for technicians at MBO level in the Netherlands. However, the demand for these courses will rise in the coming years in order to have sufficient technicians in the field by 2030-2040 who possess the knowledge and skills for hydrogen transport or distribution networks. The pilot project plans of the network operators ahead of this literature study and are already asking for the first technicians for the period 2022-2030. Action should therefore be taken to train current staff and to train additional technical personnel with knowledge of natural gas and hydrogen distribution.

Courses that cover the basic knowledge of hydrogen and the differences compared to natural gas are part of the current available training courses. A first introduction to hydrogen is already available, for example with the elective hydrogen course at Noorderpoort, the practical course in hydrogen of Kiwa Training, or other educational training provided by internal company schools.

The above is merely an introduction and a comprehensive curriculum for technical staff still has to be developed. The required attainment targets are the basis of every training and are specified in the following chapter.

Besides the scarce supply of training, attention should also be paid to the market itself, where there is a significant shortage of technically trained personnel and teachers to train them.

5. Attainment targets for technically skilled personnel in the infrastructure and distribution sector

5.1 Introduction

The majority of training courses on the market today focus primarily on teaching about the application possibilities of hydrogen, the properties of hydrogen and what using hydrogen can mean for the energy system of the future. There is still a lack of relevant training courses for technically trained personnel who, when the time comes, will need to carry out MBO-level work in and on the hydrogen network. This applies to both one-off and recurring operations.

Technically trained personnel have (often) had years of education in order to work with natural gas. They are not, or not sufficiently, trained in converting the natural gas network to the hydrogen network, in carrying out operations and in working safely in the hydrogen network. This relates to work in both the high-pressure hydrogen network (national network operators) and the low-pressure hydrogen network (regional network operators).

An attempt has been made in this study to fill this gap by setting attainment targets. Technicians will be required in the relatively short term to work on hydrogen networks. The attainment targets will help in setting up programmes or elective courses to train technicians for this work.

No safety work instructions (SWIs) are yet in place at national level. The safety instructions are currently determined individually for each network manager. This has motivated us to formulate attainment targets which, depending on the hydrogen risk assessment (RA) and the national SWIs, need to be supplemented with concrete learning objectives at a later stage.

5.2 Outcomes

The attainment targets indicate what technicians at MBO level need in terms of knowledge and skills (the ability to apply the knowledge) in order to perform their tasks on a 100% hydrogen network. These attainment targets are not intended for networks that use an H₂/methane mixture. There are many similarities between the knowledge and skills that technicians need to possess for low and high pressure. But there are differences, too, depending on the technical specifications and safety work instructions (SWIs). Technicians from the regional network operators will work close to and in the built environment. This isn't so much the case for technicians from the national network operator, as they work more with pipelines with higher pressure. This naturally filters through to the knowledge and skills that they will ultimately need. These differences are explained in the learning objectives, which can be formulated based on these attainment targets. The lack of national safety work instructions for hydrogen has been taken into account in processing the attainment targets. The underlying learning objectives therefore require further elaboration after the national safety work instructions (SWIs) for hydrogen have been established and according to the hydrogen risk assessment (RA). Moreover, the technical specifications are as yet unclear; these will have an effect on the learning objectives and not on these attainment targets.

The attainment targets are determined based on the gap analysis and on interviews with ROCs and the regional network operators represented in the expert assessment group. A definition of attainment targets and learning objectives is provided first in the paragraphs below. This is followed by an explanation of the attainment targets. Lastly, the attainment targets themselves are listed. The attainment targets are based on Bloom's taxonomy and are classified according to the ability to remember, understand and apply the knowledge learned.

5.2.1 Definition of attainment targets and learning objectives

Attainment targets give a concise description of the knowledge, insight and skills that a technician working in the hydrogen network must possess by the end of his or her training. Using the learning objectives with specific knowledge and skills as the basis, the attainment targets are given shape in a classroom setting. The curriculum looks at the steps the student needs to undertake in order to achieve the attainment targets. In accordance with the instructions of HyDelta, we have limited ourselves to formulating attainment targets.

5.2.2 Explanatory notes to the attainment targets

The attainment targets describe what a person needs to know and be able to do at the end of a study programme. It is up to the educational institution to formulate the learning objectives for the training course based on the attainment targets.

The hydrogen risk assessment (RA) is used as a starting point in establishing the learning objectives. It is essential that the RA is supplemented with the necessary measures to control the risks. The RA is divided into work situations.

Note: for each network company, a start has been made with developing work instructions (WIs) for specific work situations. If these WIs are deemed 'adequate' after a certain period, they will be forged into national safety work instructions (SWI). We are still years away from this milestone. The first SWIs are expected to be available in 2024.

When talking about choosing the right safety measures in a given work situation, the work situation relates to the risk assessment (RA) and the accompanying WIs. Examples of work situations are: converting the natural gas network to a hydrogen network, commissioning the network, and locating leaks and securing the surrounding area. In addition, working in high-pressure and low-pressure networks also requires different approaches and skill sets. These differences are given shape at the learning objective level, and not at the attainment target level, and are based on the various work situations.

The participants have an educational background in natural gas and perform work in the natural gas network with the corresponding VIAG designation. They are all familiar with natural gas concepts and terminologies. Many do the work based on history and their technical experience in natural gas. Although it is important to explain the differences between the two gases and the associated work that is involved, the focus of the lesson material should be on working in the hydrogen network. The reason why this is so important is because the students learn to use these specific operating procedures when working in the hydrogen network, and do not constantly spend time making comparisons between the tasks.

The attainment targets are designed to make participants aware of the risks and measures involved in working on the hydrogen network. The participants should be able to adapt their behaviour and attitude to the risks they face during their work. A sense of awareness needs to be created as to why certain safety measures are chosen and why certain tasks are done differently to similar tasks in the natural gas network. They need to demonstrate that they are capable of applying the safety measures during the work and, in doing so, taking the risks on which these measures are based into account. It is therefore important that sufficient attention is paid to risk awareness, behaviour, attitude and resulting actions during the course programme.

The VIAG (Safety Instructions for Natural Gas) fulfils a number of roles. These different roles should be considered when developing the curriculum. For example, an operations manager is the highest role in the VIAG for the operation. More is expected of the operations manager than just basic knowledge of gas. They need to be able to explain and back up in clear terms why certain tasks are performed and why they are done differently than in the natural gas network. In other words, there are different expectations within the various VIAG roles.

5.2.3 Attainment targets

Remember

Identify the reasons behind the use of hydrogen and the possible applications.

Identify the physical and chemical properties of hydrogen.

Identify the differences in physical and chemical properties between natural gas and hydrogen.

Identify the reasons for using an inert gas when working with hydrogen.

Identify the risks involved in working with hydrogen.

Identify the risks involved in mixing various (inert) gases with hydrogen.

Identify the measures that need to be taken based on the risks associated with the various gases.

Identify the measures that need to be taken to prevent hydrogen and air mixing.

Understand

Translate the consequences of differences in physical and chemical properties of natural gas and hydrogen to the practical work situation as described in the safety work instructions.

Explain the (safety) risks to be considered when working in the hydrogen network.

Explain the (safety) risks associated with working with inert gases.

Explain which (safety) risks occur when working with different gas mixtures.

Explain which safety measures and actions are different when working in the hydrogen network as opposed to working in the natural gas network.

Apply

In a given work situation, take the correct personal safety measures when working with hydrogen in order to reduce and control the risks.

In a given work situation, take the appropriate safety measures for the surrounding area when working with hydrogen in order to reduce and control the risks.

In a given work situation, use the correct PPE, tools and measuring equipment when working on the hydrogen network.

Explain the risks associated with responding to emergencies in the hydrogen network to the emergency services and the surrounding area.

5.3 Conclusion

The above attainment targets provide the basis for elective courses and refresher courses for technicians who will be working on the conversion and maintenance of regional distribution network pipelines up to 8 bar and high-pressure hydrogen pipelines of more than 40 bar. Central to this are general knowledge about hydrogen, (changes in) technical process steps and safe working procedures. A detailed elaboration of the attainment targets in the form of learning objectives can be further developed after establishing national safety work instructions (SWIs) for hydrogen and after clarifying the technical specifications.

6. Conclusion

In the field of infrastructure technology (energy distribution in the forms of (natural) gas, heat and electricity), the educational institutes do not offer any curricula that focus on hydrogen. The demand for hydrogen education will certainly grow in the coming years to ensure that there will be sufficient technicians with knowledge and skills for a hydrogen transport or distribution network by 2030-2040. The pilot project plans of the network operators are ahead of this literature study and are already asking for the first technicians in the period 2022-2030. Action should therefore be taken to train current staff and to train additional technical personnel with knowledge of natural gas and hydrogen distribution.

Courses that cover the basic knowledge of hydrogen and the differences compared to natural gas are part of the current available trainings. A first introduction to hydrogen is already available, for example with the elective hydrogen course offered at Noorderpoort, the practical course in hydrogen of Kiwa Training, or other educational training provided by in-company schools.

A comprehensive training course for technical personnel is not available and will have to be developed. The required attainment targets serve as the basis for every training course and study programme. These attainment targets are specified in Chapter 5. This forms the basis for electives and refresher courses for technicians who will be working on the conversion and maintenances of high-pressure and low-pressure hydrogen pipelines. General knowledge about hydrogen, (changes in) technical process steps and safe working procedures are central topics. A detailed elaboration of the attainment targets in the form of learning objectives can be further developed after establishing national safety work instructions (SWIs) for hydrogen and after clarifying the technical specifications.

In addition to the scarce educational offer, there is also a widespread shortage on the labour market. This applies to students as well as teachers of infrastructure technology. It is imperative to address these issues sooner rather than later, as the transition to hydrogen can only be carried out if the operational staff (and the teachers who educate and train them) are actually available.

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I. Annex I

The table below shows all schools that emerged from the website research that in some way include hydrogen in their study programmes. The schools highlighted in green have been selected for further research by means of interviews.

Educational institute	Hydrogen activities	Level
Albeda	No activity in hydrogen, but collaborations with Technology College Rotterdam (see separate line)	MBO
Aventus	Project 'Driving on Hydrogen'. The TU Delft and DEAC in Teuge assisted with guided tours and guest lectures on hydrogen technology.	MBO
Koning Willem I College	Course programme: (first) technician gas, water and heat distribution. Ask to what extent they pay attention to hydrogen. They use teaching aids from the BLEI foundation.	MBO
MBO Amersfoort/school for technology	Offer courses in (first) technician in distribution technology. They call themselves the region's technical sustainable educators. They keep up with the latest developments in the energy transition.	MBO
MBO Rijnland	Smart Technology. 'The Next Generation Housing Estate' – a so-called living lab where MBO students of Smart Technology, Construction, Installation Technology and Electrical Engineering work together on the energy transition. Students contribute ideas on how to get neighbourhoods off natural gas sooner. Collaboration with Stedin, Van Dorp Installaties, Dura Vermeer, WC Vidomes, Bébouw Midreth and the municipality of Zoetermeer. Include sustainable energy technology in their courses on electrical installations.	MBO
ROC A12/Technova college	Course programme for mechanical systems technician. Hydrogen developments that pertain to automotive engineering (cooperative projects with practical learning and students).	MBO
ROC Midden Nederland	The Tech College of ROCMN has received a subsidy for sustainable mobility and sustainable energy and will use the funding to adapt its current curriculum and develop new study programmes. Also takes part in innovation week on sustainability	MBO
ROC Nijmegen	Once a year, ROC Nijmegen organises a sustainability week in which students work in groups (e.g. hydrogen is on the agenda). For construction and engineering students.	MBO

	Education for middle management engineering officer, mechanical engineering, energy engineering.	
ROC Rivor	Smart Technology Experience Centre (education, government and businesses together). Students receive training and education to work in the energy transition. Set up a Smart Building course with a strong focus on innovation, sustainability, etc.	MBO
Summa College	Hydrogen is only given some coverage in study programmes relating to an automotive career.	MBO
Techniek College Rotterdam	September 2020, Vocational Campus in Middelharnis where professionals are trained for the energy transition and sustainable energy technologies. Four new courses started in September 2020, where students learn how to install and maintain the successor to the central heating boiler.	MBO
Alfa-college	Training module Hydrogen Works, part of the study programme Engineering Technician, BOL level 4. Also available for companies. Students work together on building a hydrogen-powered tiny house and a speedboat on hydrogen; helped with opening Hystock	MBO
Deltion College	Hydrogen project with third-year automotive technicians, not much else	MBO
Drenthe College	New elective course called “Hydrogen technology in industry”, a collaboration with companies and Noorderpoort College, beginning next academic year. Has a hydrogen education centre together with Alfacollege, more for primary and secondary education. Teachers have attended several master classes on hydrogen.	MBO
Friesland College	Hydrogen-powered cars are explained in the mobile technology course; water technology is an elective course as part of the automotive technical specialist study programme.	MBO
Noorderpoort	Already has training courses on hydrogen. They are also working on new hydrogen modules; see the leaflet in Teams. The contact person at Noorderpoort is Roeland Hogt. They work together with other MBO schools in Energy College, Gas 2.0 and with universities and colleges in the Green Hydrogen Booster project, among others.	MBO
ROC Friese Poort	Not much information, but involved in Energy College	MBO
ROC Nova College	No information, but does offer a study programme for sustainable energy consultant	MBO
SOMA College	Training courses for trade professionals, foremen, superintendents, etc. To prepare mechanics, technicians and engineers of the future for this new world, the SOMA	MBO

	<p>College training institute in Harderwijk plans to gradually make the switch to electric and hydrogen energy next academic year. In road construction, the machines will change from diesel to electrified. And they are looking into the possibility of generating hydrogen on building sites. SOMA college has amended the name of its training programme from Vehicle Mechanic and Mobile Equipment to Vehicle Technician and Mobile Equipment. Components are 'zero-emission equipment', new drive technologies, and electric and hydrogen engines.</p>	
Kiwa Training	<p>Kiwa Training offers a number of e-learning modules that focus on hydrogen: Miniature fuel cells, production and handling, introduction to fuel cells and hydrogen, CHP plants with fuel cells, fuel cells for transport applications, generators based on fuel cells. Kiwa Training also has a practice-oriented hydrogen course that delves into the properties of hydrogen and how hydrogen acts and reacts in practice. The course uses a hydrogen table for performing practical tests. The Practical Course on Hydrogen is intended for technicians, foremen, superintendents, safety experts and other technicians in the energy sector, as well as for all other professionals who expect work with hydrogen in their jobs. In addition, hydrogen is included in the study programmes Sustainable Energy and Heat Distribution, Energy Transition: Gas Technology, Energy Transition and Sustainable Energy. Kiwa has built a hydrogen house on its campus (Hydrogen Experience Centre), where technicians can receive practical training in converting the natural gas network to a hydrogen network.</p>	MBO, MBO+, HBO
Energy College	<p>Offers master classes in the field of hydrogen aimed at developments and collaborations at the ROCs. The H2 speedboat is one of the examples. Energy College is a partnership between schools. It is a platform for innovation, education and a meeting place for professionals and pioneers in the energy sector in the north of the Netherlands.</p>	MBO
PHOE (post-HBO studies in Energy)	<p>The Sustainable Energy programme includes a hydrogen component. Participants are often employees of municipalities, provinces, water boards and energy companies. Eligibility to enrol in the post-HBO Sustainable Energy study: a higher vocational education level (HBO) or equivalent is desirable. In addition, they offer the course 'Introduction to Energy Management'. After completing the Introduction to Energy Management course, students will have attained the basic knowledge necessary to solve energy issues. This study programme aims to turn students into energy experts, with sufficient all-round knowledge to determine the measures that are needed to maximise the energy management in businesses and in homes. To enrol</p>	MBO+/HBO

	<p>in the post-HBO Introduction to Energy Management study programme, participants are required to have at least a technical and professional background at higher vocational (HBO) level. Participants are mostly (energy) consultants, facility managers, licensing officers and employees of technical services.</p>	
<p>Energy Delta Institute</p>	<p>In cooperation with DNV and Waterstofnet, Energy Delta Institute organises hydrogen master classes. The master class is presented by experts in the field and give attendees a comprehensive overview of the entire hydrogen value chain, the role of hydrogen in the energy transition, the development of costs and volumes, technological developments and various forms of hydrogen storage. Attention is also paid to the transport of hydrogen, flexible properties and end-use applications, and the prospects of a green hydrogen economy in the future. The future opportunities and business models of hydrogen and the perspective of a hydrogen economy are discussed in detail. It provides a complete overview of the hydrogen value chain, realistic insight into the future possibilities of hydrogen and offers an exchange of knowledge with experts and colleagues. You learn: the possibilities and impossibilities of hydrogen, latest developments, technological challenges (including transport), earnings model for hydrogen. The master class is intended for professionals inside and outside the energy sector who want to learn about the entire hydrogen value chain, with a special focus on the northern Netherlands. They also offer an intensive hydrogen course. The three-day course discusses at length the legislation surrounding hydrogen and looks at various business cases. Together with Brunel, EDI offers a post-HBO study in the field of hydrogen. Topics that are covered in depth include the energy transition, the hydrogen value chain, transport, regulations and system integration.</p>	<p>MBO+, HBO, University</p>
<p>SOMA company training courses</p>	<p>Training provider in infrastructure technology. Nothing specific can be found about hydrogen. More information has been requested regarding how much attention is given to hydrogen is covered in the training courses, for instance for first technician in gas, water and heating.</p>	<p>MBO</p>
<p>PAO Techniek</p>	<p>Provides hydrogen training for professionals on the properties and applications of hydrogen. It is not geared to the work that is performed in the hydrogen network. The training gives answers to questions such as what role hydrogen plays in the energy system and why hydrogen is or should be chosen. The following topics are covered during the course:</p>	<p>MBO, MBO+, HBO</p>

	<p>The role of hydrogen in the energy system</p> <p>Relevant physical properties and calculation examples</p> <p>Storage and transport</p> <p>Application examples for power, light and heat</p> <p>Fuel cells, operation and application</p> <p>Generation: reforming, electrolysis, purification</p> <p>Application: field lab for the local generation of electrolysis, storage and filling station</p>	
Van Empel opleidingen	<p>The main focus is on installation engineering. Offers a workshop: what you need to know about hydrogen. Technicians, engineers, work planners, project leaders and facility managers who want to be informed about the developments in the energy transition “from natural gas to hydrogen gas”. The following topics are covered:</p> <p>What opportunities does hydrogen offer?</p> <p>What are the application areas of hydrogen?</p> <p>What is hydrogen?</p> <p>Why move from natural gas to hydrogen?</p> <p>Advantages and disadvantages of hydrogen;</p> <p>Hydrogen and environmental requirements;</p> <p>Standards and standardisation;</p> <p>What can/should I do with my installation(s);</p> <p>Room for asking questions and discussing received documentation.</p>	MBO, MBO+, HBO
Everything about Hydrogen	<p>Everything about Hydrogen organises a one-day practical course on hydrogen. Topics that are covered: What is hydrogen? How do you make hydrogen? How do you store and transport hydrogen? What are the possible applications in the built environment, transport and industry? How safe is hydrogen? What role can hydrogen play in the energy transition? Besides theory, there are demonstrations showing how hydrogen is made, a miniature hydrogen-powered car, a hydrogen scooter and a hydrogen drone, as well as a hydrogen cooking hob.</p>	MBO, MBO+, HBO
Berghauser Pont Academy	<p>Offers a one-day course on hydrogen. The course explains what hydrogen is, why it is relevant to achieving climate objectives, which applications are interesting in the context of energy transition, how the hydrogen chain works, which safety and other issues are important, where hydrogen fits</p>	HBO

	<p>into government policy and the legal framework, and which target groups are affected? The course is intended for policy officers for sustainability and energy transition, project leaders and lawyers who are involved in drawing up regional energy strategies and projects for sustainable energy infrastructure, and (environmental) advisers working for municipalities, environmental services and provinces. In addition, the course can be interesting for employees of companies that see hydrogen as a promising prospect.</p>	
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